

Renewable Energy Trends Analysis: A Patents Study

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Abstract—This article explains the elements and considerations taken into account when implementing and applying patent evaluation and scientometric study in the identifications of technology trends, and the tools that led to the implementation of a software application for patent revision. Univariate analysis helped recognize the technological leaders in the field of energy, and steered the way for a multivariate analysis of this sample, which allowed for a graphical description of the techniques of mature technologies, as well as the detection of emerging technologies. This article ends with a validation of the methodology as applied to the case of fuel cells.

Keywords—Energy, technology mapping, patents.

I. INTRODUCTION

TECHNOLOGICAL surveillance refers to “the organization making the continuous, systematic, organized effort to observe, gather, analyze, and accurately spread and recall information about the facts of its economic, technological, social or commercial environment which are relevant to it due to their ability for signaling an opportunity or a threat for it” [1], [2]. The cited authors pose “what” and “how” as the two key questions for starting any benchmarking project. Reference [3] proposes to obtain from technological maps information about what is occurring in a specific technological area: what subjects are being researched, what are the emerging lines of research, what are the leading researcher companies and teams, among other aspects [4].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Representativeness

This process of patent revision is taken as a census, because all of the individuals (patents) having the characteristics of the object of study are taken into account [5]. The patents analyzed in this study were selected from the United States Patent Office database, freely accessible via internet at <http://www.uspto.gov>.

B. Patent Selection

The study was limited to the innovations generated in the last five years. In line with this criterion, the selected patents have an application date between January 1st, 2000 (01/01/2000) and July 13th, 2005 (13/07/2005).

The second criterion consisted in that the patents should include in any field the keywords selected by the research team. These were the words biomass, energy, and generation. The combinations of these words resulted in three database queries with the criteria: biomass; energy and generation, and lastly energy and biomass.

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C. Storage

Seeking ease of storage, formatting and further processing, the decision was made to save only the abstract of the patents, because this allowed to perform the study with minimum loss of non-representative information.

This is justified in the fact that the information under study is present in both the abstract and the full text of a patent.

Two tools of the Microsoft Office suite were employed for storage and depuration of the initial information: Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel. They were chosen because of their relatively low cost and high penetration in the Colombian workplace. Storage in word processor format was temporary and followed two reasons: the difficulty of directly transferring the text of the patent to a spreadsheet with the desired format, and the convenience of some editing features absent in Excel and needed for the application of the selected tool.

D. Processing

Once duplicated entries were deleted, the most words that appeared with the most frequency in the selected patents were identified.

The most frequent words were purged of adverbs, adjectives and other words that for grammatical reasons tend to reappear but do not constitute a trend or a significant contribution to the studied technique.

In these revision a list of excluded words was made, and is shown in Table I.

TABLE I
EXCLUDED WORDS EXAMPLE

a	as	for	may	than
above	be	has	not	The
an	between	into	or	thereby
any	can	it	so	this

Besides, a synonym list was built as well. It comprises those words that, despite not having exactly the same meaning, are considered as such for the technical purpose of reducing the number of keywords and, therefore, dispersion.

With the lists of excluded words and synonyms completed, the patents underwent revision prior to the elaboration of a table where the intersection of each patent with a given keyword corresponded to zero (0) if it was not found, and to one (1) otherwise.

II. UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF THE PATENTS

Univariate analysis helps identify other important aspects for competitive intelligence, such as technological leaders (countries or institutions that hold the most patents on a subject), as well as a specific subject's growth or decrement in

Observation of the sustained growth of patent applications with the word fuel prompts the suspicion that a technological trend exists involving both words fuel and cell. A revision of the technological leaders found that three out of the top seven patent holders have product lines with fuel cells, which may mean that a trend has been detected.

- Group 4: Composed of the words electric, battery, current, voltage, circuit, capacitor, among others. This group corresponds clearly to innovations in devices for

conventional ways of generation of electricity.

- Group 5: Left unmarked due to its diversity and illegibly superimposed items. A more detailed analysis of this group requires the strategy shown below.

A trend appears in a technological map as a set of words that appear near each other and separated from the central items. A trend can be confirmed by tracing a new map, where the words corresponding to other groups suspected to constitute trends as well are intentionally left out.

Fig. 2 Technological map of energy generation, traced without taking biomass into consideration

Observation of Fig. 2 confirms the fuel cell trend, because once the information corresponding to biomass is left out, this group stays together, far from the central cloud (group 1) in Fig. 2. It is possible to notice how the identified trends move, but the structure of the clusters remain.

It is noteworthy to remark on the presence of group 4, which contains the words anode, catode, methanol, hydrogen and membrane, which serve to explain the functioning and classification of fuel cells. Also, the groups related to electricity and steam-based generation (groups 2 and 3) are still observed.

Upon deletion of the words corresponding to fuel cells, the biomass-based energy generation trend is confirmed. However, specifications about how these innovations work cannot be drawn from this map.

The terms closest to biomass relate to water, carbon, waste,

compression, and reactors. Next to the origin point are the terms biogas, biofuel and biowaste, but not close enough to biomass to assume a direct link as explained by the map. This could be construed as a normal feature of an expanding technique where efforts are not directed toward specific aspects, but towards isolated or disjointed initiatives. The groups linked to electricity and steam reappear here.

In order to find explanations to what was observed near the origin point, a further map was made (not shown here) in which both trends were absent. There, the groups of words that had appeared since the beginning, corresponding to electricity and steam-based energy generation, remain predominant. With this methodology, two emerging technologies were identified, and as many mature technologies were confirmed. One of the detected technologies, biomass-based energy generation, is of a general nature, and the other

of auxiliary energy in electric cars. This application is ideal for urban areas because a vehicle with an electric engine can have excellent torque.

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